
WALTON CENTER FOR PLANETARY HEALTH | 777 E UNIVERSITY DR, TEMPE, AZ 85281

January 14, 2026

To Whom It May Concern,

This letter serves as formal confirmation that the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) is recognized as the first official regional node of the Earth BioGenome Project (EBP).

The Earth BioGenome Project is a global initiative with the mission to sequence, catalog, and characterize the genomes of all known eukaryotic species on Earth. Regional nodes play a critical role in advancing this mission by coordinating scientific activities, infrastructure, data generation, and community engagement within defined geographic regions, in alignment with EBP standards and principles.

ERGA has been formally acknowledged by the Earth BioGenome Project as fulfilling this role for Europe, beginning in May 2025. As the first officially designated EBP regional node, ERGA has demonstrated leadership in building a coordinated, collaborative framework for reference genome generation, data sharing, and capacity building, fully consistent with the goals and governance of the Earth BioGenome Project.

This recognition reflects ERGA's commitment to high-quality genomics, open science, ethical sampling, and international collaboration, and establishes ERGA as a foundational component of the global EBP network.

Please consider this letter as official confirmation of ERGA's status within the Earth BioGenome Project. Should further information or verification be required, the Earth BioGenome Project Secretariat would be pleased to provide additional details.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Harris A. Lewin".

Harris A. Lewin, Ph.D.
Chair, Earth BioGenome Project Executive Council